

ANALYSIS OF THE BEST PRACTICES OF BIOMASS SUPPLY FOR ENERGY PRODUCTION**Tetiana Zheliezna***Institute of Engineering Thermophysics of the National Academy of Sciences
Ukraine**03057, Marii Kapnist Street, 2a, Kyiv**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14049636>***Abstract**

The purpose of the article is to consider, analyse and compare approaches to logistics of different biomass types. The focus is on primary agricultural residues, felling residues and biomass from the pruning of agricultural plantations. For biomass delivered to a conversion facility, the logistics expenditures may come to 30-50% of its total cost. That means that planning biomass fuel supply may affect economic performance or even feasibility of a biomass project. There are four main elements of economic relations in biomass for energy supply chain: harvesting, storage, pre-treatment, and transportation. A biomass plant operator can carry out all these elements himself, be responsible for one or several elements or hire specialized companies to complete all the stages of biomass supply. These options have advantages and disadvantages related to responsibility, operability, efficiency, and other issues. Biomass exchanges and trade-logistic centres are considered reliable and effective means to provide biomass facilities with biomass fuel. Biomass exchanges operate on national and international levels while trade-logistic centres are mostly engaged in local or regional deliveries.

Keywords: biomass, biomass fuel, wood biomass, felling residues, agricultural residues.

Introduction.

Bioenergy has become an important part of the global energy sector, replacing fossil fuels and contributing to greenhouse gases emission reduction. Now, the share of bioenergy in the total final energy consumption is more than 12%, totalling about 46 exajoules (EJ) a year. The production of derived heat by modern bioenergy has exceeded 1.3 EJ/y in the world, over half of it being obtained from solid biomass. As for biofuels, bioethanol accounts for nearly 2/3 of the total production which reached a record level of 170 billion litres (4.3 EJ) in 2022. The use of biogas and biomethane has been one of the most promising directions of bioenergy development lately. The global production of these gaseous fuels amounted to more than 1.6 EJ in 2022, about 50% of this volume being obtained in Europe.

The average technical potential of primary energy production from biomass in the world is estimated at about 200 EJ/y by 2030 and 600 EJ/y by 2050. At that, the figures for the average global sustainable potential are 100 EJ/y by 2030 and 140 EJ/y by 2050 (Geletukha 2021). This shows availability of biomass feedstock for further sustainable development of the bioenergy sector.

Worldwide, numerous types of biomass originate from plant cultivation, animal husbandry, forestry, food industry and other sources. Generally, biomass residues can be classified into primary, secondary, and tertiary groups (Ayub 2023). The primary residues (straw, corn and sunflower stalks, felling residues, stems, leaves) are leftovers of main food crops and forest products. The secondary residues (sunflower husk, rice hulls, sugarcane bagasse, wood chips) are biomass waste produced during the processing of food crops and wood for other valuable products. The biodegradable fraction of municipal solid waste, used cooking oil, manure and other biomass types of similar nature can be described as tertiary biomass residue produced when humans or animals consume the biomass-derived products (food,

feed, materials) (Van Stralen 2016). Taking into consideration sustainability and waste management issues, one can state that at present, energy production from biomass is powered by agro-industrial lignocellulosic biomass and agro-industrial wastes (Nair 2022). In addition, it is important that the global tendency is moving towards circular economy systems and sustainable sources of feedstock (Kumar 2023).

A biomass supply and use chain typically consists of the following elements: biomass harvesting, collection, storage and transportation; biomass pre-treatment and conversion to the final products such as biofuels, biomass fuels, energy; distribution of final products to users (Kousar 2023). For biomass delivered to a conversion facility, the logistics expenditures may come to 30-50% of its total cost (Schouwenberg 2015). The upper value is for long supply chains of biomass and biomass fuels, for example for overseas transportation of wood pellets.

The article considers different approaches to supplying and trading solid biomass for energy production. The focus is on primary agricultural residues, felling residues and biomass from the pruning of agricultural plantations. Agri-biomass and felling residues are well-known and widely used types of biomass, while biomass from pruning orchards and vineyards is a comparatively new type of residues in the bioenergy sector. The production of fuel and energy from pruned biomass is developing dynamically, especially in Europe (Geletukha 2018a, Drahnev 2021).

Methodology.

Solid biomass can be supplied in different forms such as pellets, briquettes, bales, loose residues, which considerably affect the logistics and its cost. Compressed biomass (pellets, briquettes) has much less specific volume and higher energy density as compared to loose residues (chaffed straw). That means that the compressed biomass requires fewer transportation trips to be delivered to the end user and occupies less storage space. For example, straw can be supplied in the form

of rectangular and round bales, briquettes, pellets, or just as chaffed straw. Of these forms, the biggest energy density (7.8-11.2 GJ/m³) falls to straw pellets (Table 1)

(Geletukha 2017a, Skott 2020). Specific energy content of the pellets is 5-7 times as high as that of bales, let alone the chaffed straw.

Table 1. Trade forms of straw for energy and their characteristics.

Characteristics	Briquettes	Pellets	Bales			Chaffed straw
			Small bales	Big bales*	Round bales	
Typical size (weight)	Diameter > 25 mm	Diameter < 25 mm	70-90×46×36 cm (12-15 kg)	2.3-2.5×1.2×1.3 m (450-650 kg)	Diameter 1.7 m Length 1.2 m (220-270 kg)	10-200 mm
Bulk density (D), kg/m ³	300-700	500-700	70-160		70-110	40-60
			90-100**	140-170**	100-120**	
Specific volume (1/D), m ³ /t	1.4-3.3	1.4-2.0	6-14		9-14	16-25
Specific energy content, GJ/m ³	4.7-11.2	7.8-11.2	1.01-2.3		1.01-1.58	0.57-0.86

* There are also mini-big bags (2.0-2.4×0.8×0.8 m) and midi-big bales (2.3-2.5×1.2×0.9 m), for example in Denmark.

** Density.

Trucks are commonly used vehicles in a solid biomass supply chain. An important characteristic of the vehicle is its workload. Taking a 110 m³ truck with the trailer as an example, one can calculate that it can transport only 5.5 t of chaffed straw while the theoretical cargo weight for biomass pellets is more than 70 t (Table 2). The actual cargo weight is restricted by national limits for the load carrying capacity, which is, for

instance, 22 t in Ukraine. Thus, the workload of the truck with trailer is 25% for chaffed straw (5.5 t/22 t), 60% for big straw bales (13.2 t/22 t) and 100% for biomass pellets, woodchips, and firewood (see Table 2). So, to enhance feasibility of a bioenergy project, project planners should deeply consider the logistics with the object to avoid or at least limit transporting biomass of low bulk density.

Table 2. Workload of a truck with trailer for different biomass fuels.

Biomass fuel type	Bulk density (typical), kg/m ³	Low heating value (typical), MJ/kg	Energy density, MJ/m ³	Workload of a truck with the trailer of 110 m ³ , t
	(a)	(b)	(c)=(a)×(b)	(d)=(a)×110 m ³ /1000*
Chaffed straw	50	14	700	5.5
Loose sunflower husk	95	16	1520	10.5
Big straw bales	120**	14	1680	13.2***
Pellets: - straw	650	15	9750	22
- wood	650	17	11050	22
- sunflower husk	650	17	11050	22
Wood chips	250	10	2500	22
Firewood	320	10	3200	22
Sawdust	150	10	1500	16.5
Felling residues	150	10	1500	16.5

* The maximum weight of a truck depends on the number of axles. If the actual weight of the cargo of a fully loaded vehicle exceeds its carrying capacity, the maximum permissible carrying capacity of 22 tons (the value valid for Ukraine) is taken. But for the maximum permissible carrying capacity, the workload of the vehicle could be 71.5 t for pellets, 27.5 t for wood chips, 35.2 t for firewood.

** It is calculated based on the bale weight (13.2 t) and vehicle volume (110 m³). This considers the fact that the bales must find room on the vehicle.

*** The figure is for 24 bales (12 on the truck, 12 on the trailer): 550 kg (the average weight of a big bale) × 24 = 13.2 t.

Another important point is the transportation distance. For solid biomass, to be efficiently delivered to a conversion facility by trucks, the typical distance should be within 50-100 km. Usually, bioenergy project planners take this into consideration and try to follow the rule, which one can see from available descriptions of successful projects. For example, when DuPont company produced bioethanol from corn stover in Iowa (USA) in 2015-2018, the feedstock was supplied by farmers within the radius of 48 km (Drahniev 2016). After 2018 the production of bioethanol ceased, however it was not in the least connected with the logistics of biomass supply.

An approach to the logistics of biomass supply for energy production depends on the type of feedstock and its source. Poor logistics may affect feasibility of the whole project and vice versa. Planning logistics should be a key element of a bioenergy project development. It may even influence the choice of location and capacity of a bioenergy facility.

Main part.

Main sources of biomass are agriculture, forestry, wood processing industry, food industry, municipal engineering (in terms of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste) and activity on growing energy crops. Agriculture generates residues and wastes of numerous types including straw, stalks, biomass from pruning,

manure. In contrast to the primary agricultural residues (straw, stalks) which arise directly on field during harvesting crops, the secondary residues (husk, hull, bagasse) are generated at enterprises of food industry while processing crops. Forestry and woodworking industry are sources of many wood fuels and residues such as firewood, woodchips, felling residues, sawdust. Energy crops (willow, miscanthus, poplar, switchgrass etc.) are cultivated with the direct purpose of production of biomass fuel and energy.

Biomass for energy should be used deeply considering sustainability issues such as influence on soil and biodiversity. First, this applies to primary agricultural residues and felling residues which must be partly left on field and in forest. For instance, in Denmark, the most experienced European country in energy production from straw, only about 30% of the whole annual amount of straw is used as fuel at biomass facilities; the rest is left on field (40%) and utilised in animal husbandry (30%) (Zheliezna 2022). As for logging residues, minimum 20% of them is typically left in forests in the EU countries (Nilsson 2016).

Some selected examples of the best practices of biomass supply to bioenergy plants are presented in Table 3. The examples from the EU countries, England, the USA and Ukraine cover agricultural residues, wood biomass and biomass from pruning.

Table 3. Examples of the best practices of biomass supply logistics.

Biomass plant	Location	Biomass type and consumption amount	Biomass supply details
Boiler plant 1 MW	Ulbjerg, Denmark	Straw (1000 t/y); additional fuel: woodchips, sawdust	Straw in big bales is supplied by local farmers. Local trade.
Two 8.5 MW boilers	Ringsted, Denmark	Straw	Baled straw is supplied by local farmers. Trade based on tenders with contracts for 1-3 years.
CHP plant 38 MW _e + 110 MW _{th}	Lisbjerg, Denmark	Straw (240 kt/y); additional fuel: woodchips (up to 50%)	Local farmers supply baled straw. Wholesale trade.
CHP plant 38.5 MW _e	Sleaford, England	Straw (240 kt/y); additional fuel: woodchips (up to 20%)	Straw in big bales is delivered by energy company Eco2. The delivery distance is within 80 km.
Boiler plant 250 kW	Murillo de Gallego, Spain	Straw (280 t/y)	The boiler plant owners supply straw in big bales from their own fields.
Two 5 MW boilers	Nikopol, Ukraine	Straw	The boiler plant owners supply straw in big bales from their own fields. Straw harvesting period is two months (July, August).
Bioethanol plant of 113 mln l/y; operated in 2015-2018.	Nevada, USA	Corn stover (700 kt/y)	Biomass was delivered from local farmers' fields within 48 km by contracts.
Boilers of 2 MW, 0.8 MW, and 2 MW	Energy cooperative Eno Energia, Finland	Woodchips	Main part of woodchips is supplied from local forests that belong to the cooperative members.
Boiler 700 kW	Oberrospe bioenergy village, Germany	Woodchips	Woodchips are supplied by energy cooperative which includes 7 bioenergy villages.
CHP plant 5.7 MW _e + 10 MW _{th}	Karlovac, Croatia	Woodchips (> 76 kt/y)	Biomass is delivered by the state company Hrvatske Šume which is responsible for the national forest management.

CHP plant 23 MW _e + 60 MW _{th}	Järvenpää, Finland	Woodchips; additional fuel: wood and paperboard waste, horse manure (20%)	Woodchips are supplied from forests and sawmills within 100 km.
CHP plant 130 MW _e + 280 MW _{th}	Stokholm, Sweden	Woodchips (3 mln m ³ /y)	60% is imported and delivered by sea in containers; 40% is transported by railway from national forests.
Boilers of 600 kW and 250 kW	Wieniawa, Poland	Straw; additional fuel: biomass from apple tree pruning	Biomass is supplied by local company which owns fruit orchards.
Boiler 400 kW	Vilafranca del Penedès, Spain	Pruned grapevine (225 t/y)	Biomass is collected and delivered from 45 local farmers within 15 km.
Steam boiler 1.16 MW	Shabo, Ukraine	Pruned grapevine (1-1.5 kt/y)	Biomass is supplied from fields of the boiler plant owners within 10 km.

A feature of straw supply logistics is rather limited period of time available for its collection. Typically, straw should be collected within two weeks after harvesting cereal crops so that the field would be free for further agricultural operations. Another feature is transportation of straw bales from local farms or agricultural companies within limited distance, usually 50-100 km. For instance, in Denmark straw is supplied by farmers, agricultural cooperatives and the association which include farmers who specialize in straw supply (the Danish organization of straw suppliers). Straw is traded locally (1-3 farmers supply biomass to a boiler plant or a CHP plant of small/medium capacity), on wholesale basis (an energy company purchases a lot of biomass from regional farmers and delivers it to big energy facilities), and by tenders (bids are taken from individual farmers, groups of farmers and cooperatives) or auctions in which the Danish organization of straw suppliers participates (Zheliezna 2024). These types of straw market can be found in Danish examples presented in Table 3.

Woodchips are most often produced from felling residues. There are three main approaches to this: (1) the comminution of felling residues by mobile chippers directly on site of their generation in forest; (2) hauling logging residues by forwarders to the roadside and production of woodchips there by tractor-mounted chippers or by chipper-trucks; (3) baling or bundling logging residues followed by their transportation to a biomass plant and production of woodchips at the plant site (Geletukha 2018b). Regular biomass deliveries require certain routes which may affect nearby residential areas. The apt location of a biomass facility, especially a big one, gives opportunity to accept intensive fuel delivery without disturbing local population. Such examples are the combined heat and power (CHP) plant of 23 MW_e + 60 MW_{th} nearby Järvenpää (Finland) and CHP plant of 130 MW_e + 280 MW_{th} in the centre of Stokholm (Sweden). In the former case (Finland), the CHP plant is situated on the town outskirts near a highway and can easily take 35 trucks of wood fuel daily. In the second case (Sweden), the CHP plant is situated near the port and railway. Woodchips for the plant are delivered by sea (3-4 times a week, 60% of the annual consumption) and by railway (6 times a week, 40% of the annual consumption).

There are different options for harvesting residues from pruning orchards and vineyards, which depends on the combination and sequence of operations and machinery used. The residues can be comminuted into hog fuel or chips as well as baled. For these operations, one can use chippers, shredders, balers, and other special-purpose machinery, including innovative equipment (Pari 2018). Like primary agricultural residues, the biomass from pruning should be transported at a short distance. For example, in Vilafranca del Penedès (Spain) biomass from pruning vineyards is delivered to a 400 kW boiler plant from local farmers within 15 km radius. Winery Shabo (Ukraine) has a 1.16 MW steam boiler running on grapevine. Biomass from pruning vineyards belonging to the winery owners is collected and supplied within 10 km distance.

Findings.

On the whole, one can distinguish four main elements of the economic relations in biomass for energy supply chain: harvesting, storage, pre-treatment, and transportation (Oliinyk 2016). A biomass plant operator may carry out all the logistics elements himself, be responsible for one or several elements or just hire specialized companies to complete all the stages of biomass supply. These options have some advantages and disadvantages related to responsibility, operability, efficiency, and other issues. When the plant operator performs some stages himself, his decision to purchase new vehicles and machinery for biomass logistics operations may depend on the capacity of the biomass plant and future development plans. If the facility is big and consumes a lot of biomass or there are definite plans to increase the existing capacity, the operator can purchase new equipment without a negative economic effect on the project. Otherwise, it is recommended to use the available vehicles and machinery or rent them.

To ensure the stable and reliable fuel supply, a biomass plant operator can enjoy services of biomass exchanges. Good examples are Baltpool in Europe and Midwest Biomass Exchange in the North America. They both carry out electronic trade of biomass fuel based on contracts and quality control. By now, Baltpool includes more than 550 purchasers and sellers and has over 45,000 performed contracts, the amount of traded wood biomass being > 5 TWh. Midwest Biomass Exchange serves customers from the USA and

Canada; the assortment of biomass is very wide including primary agricultural residues, woodchips, wood pellets, sawdust, and energy crops.

An interesting and efficient conception for biomass fuel supply is so called trade-logistic centres (TLCs) (Geletukha 2018b). Classic TLCs for wood biomass supply operate in Austria. They were created with the purpose to provide bigger quantity of biomass for energy, to involve forest owners in biomass market, and to ensure high quality of biomass fuel. A striking example of a classic TLC is Leoben centre in Styria (Austria). The centre supplies woodchips and firewood to industrial enterprises, municipalities, and private consumers. TLCs for wood biomass operate also in other EU countries, for example in Germany and Slovenia, however their activity differs from the classical TLCs in Austria. In addition to wood biomass trade and supply, TLCs in other European countries are also engaged in some related activities such as operation of boiler plants and district heating networks, maintenance of biomass plants, production of wood pellets, growing energy crops, implementation of bioenergy projects.

European bioenergy experts are studying the possibility to apply the concept of TLCs for agricultural biomass. The general approach is that the biomass supply should be integrated into the usual activity of an agricultural company. A successful example of such TLC is Tschiggerl-Agrar centre in Styria. The centre was created on the basis of a company engaged in cultivation of grain crops and production of feed pellets for animals. In addition to its usual business activity, now the company supplies maize cobs and pellets from maize cobs as fuel to industrial consumers and local farmers.

Biomass exchanges and trade-logistic centres are considered reliable and effective means to provide biomass facilities with biomass fuel. Biomass exchanges operate on the national and international levels while TLCs are mostly engaged in local or regional deliveries.

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